

**A FEW INTERESTING POINTS IN REGARD TO BRONCHIAL
ASTHMA AND REPORT OF A VERY SEVERE CASE
CURED BY INTRA-NASAL SURGERY.**

DR. WILLIAM T. PATTON, New Orleans.

It is generally accepted that bronchial asthma is a neurotic affection characterized by hyperemia and turgescence of the mucosa of the small bronchial tubes and a peculiar exudate of mucin. The attack may be due to direct irritation of the bronchial mucosa, or may be induced reflexedly by irritation from other parts of body, such as cardiac, renal, stomach, intestinal, genital, uterine, nose or throat and possible eye. Cardiac and renal could be classed as mechanical, due to edema and stasis, or irritative, due to toxemia. It is the writer's opinion that the most common source of reflex irritation is the nose and throat, reflexly involving the pneumo-gastric nerves—such conditions as polypoid or suppurative ethmoiditis, deviated septa, enlarged middle turbinates, pressed upon by the septum and outer wall of the nose, hypertrophied inferior turbinates, diseased tonsils, especially the adhesive type, also lingual tonsils.

The tonsils may act in two ways, by reflex irritation and by causing slow toxemia. Should we not be able to find any trouble, or should the treatment of conditions found not improve the asthma, we are certainly justified in passing the bronchoscope and will often find one or more small ulcers or hyperemic spots in the trachea or bronchial tubes, which should be treated by application of silver, argyrol, glycerite of tannin or whatever seems proper for the condition. It is often wonderful to see the immediate improvement in these cases. Given a case of asthma, the intestinal tract should be carefully studied and treated, then the heart and kidneys should be carefully looked after. If the trouble is not located, the nose and throat should then be carefully examined and any abnormal or diseased condition removed or treated.

The case I am about to report was a most severe and obstinate one and I believe it was only through most careful and untiring nasal treatment that he was cured.

Mr. W. P., age 27, came to me October 30, 1913. He was desperate and had been to all kinds of specialists, including dietician, heart and lung specialist, osteopath and even Christian Scientist, but none gave him any relief and he wondered if his nose could be the cause of the trouble.

He has been suffering from asthma for the past ten years, at times very severe and never entirely free from some wheezing; has lost considerable weight, is not able to attend to business and as he expressed it, was ready to give up. The patient does not smoke and drinks very little.

Examination:—Nose: Septum badly deflected to left and high up, pressing on middle turbinate, deflected to right in lower part, touching hypertrophied inferior turbinate. Pus coming from right ethmoid region. Tonsils submerged but apparently not causing trouble, mucous membranes of pharynx and upper larynx all red; ears apparently normal. Submucous resection advised, to which he willingly consented. Urine shows no indican or other abnormalities; heart, normal; lungs, characteristic signs of asthma.

October 14. Complete removal of septum nasi, under cocain and novocain. October 15. Packing removed, patient passed good night and now wants to go to office. October 16. Nose healing nicely; considerable discharge from right ethmoid region; no headache, patient claims his asthma is better. November 1. Nose has been cleaned and treated every day or so. It is still slightly clogged and pus is still coming from ethmoid region. Right middle turbinate removed in order to give better drainage. Patient claims he is fairly free from asthma.

November 4. Mixed infection phylacogen (2 cc.) given subcutaneously in dorsal region. November 6. Patient had only slight reaction. November 7. Phylacogen (3 cc.). November 8. No reaction, 5 cc. given. November 10. Slight reaction, 5 cc. given. November 11. Slight reaction, 5 cc. given. November 13. Slight reaction, 5 cc. given; feeling pretty good, only slight wheezing and nose is clearing up; much less discharge. November 17. Had chest examined by internist; only asthmatic rales found. November 19. Mixed infection and pneumonia phylacogen (5 cc.). Right side of nose blocked and considerable discharge. Did not see patient again until November 29. He claims he has been feeling fine.

November 30. On account of persisting discharge from right side ethmoids curetted. January 9. Patient has been free from asthma up to a few days ago, when he contracted severe cold and his whole head became choked up. Examination of left side showed it to be all clogged up with free discharge; cleansed and treated with argyrol packs; 5 cc. phylacogen. January 12. Intense reaction from last injection; nose much improved and patient feels much better. January 14. Phylacogen (5 cc.). January 16. Phylacogen (7 cc.). January 19. Phylacogen (10 cc.). No reaction and again slight at-

tack of asthma. January 20. Not getting any reaction from 10 cc. phylacogen subcutaneously, decided to give it intravenously; 2 minims in median basilic vein. January 22. Slight reaction, 5 minims in vein. January 23. Slight reaction, 10 minims in vein. Patient slightly better and only slight reaction. January 24, 18 minims in vein. January 26, 40 minims in vein. January 28, 60 minims in vein. January 31, 75 minims in vein, all causing only slight reaction; patient improved after each dose.

I did not see patient again until February 17, when he had very little asthma, but had a very severe laryngitis; could not talk above whisper. Examination reveals arytenoids swollen and red, small ulcer in inter-arytenoid region, both cords red. Examination of smear for T. B., negative; lingual tonsils enlarged and causing irritative cough.

February 17. Has been treated daily, larynx slightly improved, lingual tonsils removed. March 2. Much improved, no asthma. March 7. Patient became overheated, danced all night and contracted another severe cold, nose clogged and discharging freely; 40 minims phylacogen intravenously. March 9, much improved. March 11, 50 minims phylacogen intravenously. March 14. Had quite a reaction from last injection but now feels fine; 20 minims phylacogen intravenously. March 29. Seen several times a week, intra-tracheal injections 10 per cent iodoform in liquid alboline and several doses phylacogen.

May 1. Larynx entirely well and looks normal, feels fine. July 6. Patient feeling fine only occasional cold in head; has good appetite; gaining weight; nose clear, and no discharge nor asthma. October 23. Heard from case only recently. He is feeling fine and happy.

This case is very interesting in that each time asthma appeared there was always some swelling and discharge in the nose, and until nose was cured of all abnormal conditions asthma persisted. Undoubtedly phylacogen was of great value in this case, for we could abort the asthma, if injection was given in time. However, I do not believe it should be used until all sources of irritation are removed, and then it should be pushed to limit and not given up after few doses. In all, the patient received 75 cc. phylacogen subcutaneously in twelve injections; 27 cc. phylacogen intravenously in fourteen injections without alarming reactions. The patient usually had a chilly sensation, pains in head and over body in about an hour, which lasted for several hours. Then he felt fine for several days.

1109 Maison Blanche Building.